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Congenital Malaria in Neonates Born to Mothers with Perinatal Malaria: A Case Series from a Malaria-Endemic Region and A Review of Literature

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ABSTRACT

Congenital malaria occurs when newborns acquire Plasmodium parasites from their mothers during pregnancy or childbirth. Although antimalarial chemoprophylaxis is routinely recommended to pregnant women in malaria endemic regions to protect them from malaria and its possible effect on the baby, cases of malaria sometimes still occur. This case series documents three neonates, identified within 6 months in a private healthcare facility in Nigeria, a malaria endemic region, who developed congenital malaria despite their mothers receiving standard antimalarial prophylaxis during pregnancy. Each baby presented with fever within the first week of life and tested positive for Plasmodium falciparum on blood smear microscopy with parasitemia levels that ranged from 57 to 95 parasites per microliter. Sepsis screen including blood cultures were negative in all three infants. The three neonates received oral artemether-lumefantrine and recovered completely within three to ten days. A consistent pattern emerged where symptomatic congenital malaria diagnosis was closely linked to perinatal maternal malaria. Knowing a mother's malaria parasitemia status could help predict which sick newborn babies would need malaria screening, potentially reducing unnecessary antibiotics and sepsis workups.

Keywords: Congenital malaria, Neonatal malaria, Plasmodium falciparum, Perinatal malaria transmission, case series, Maternal-fetal transmission, Neonatal fever.

INTRODUCTION

Malaria kills more than 600,000 people annually, mainly in sub-Saharan Africa, with children under five and pregnant women bearing the heaviest burden (WHO, 2025). This is because young children have not yet developed immunity to the parasite, while pregnant women have reduced malaria immunity as parasites sequester in the placenta. Congenital malaria (CM), is the presence of malaria parasites in the peripheral blood of a newborn within the first 7 days of life, following in-utero infection or transmission to the baby during birth (Andarge & Almaw, 2025; Omidiji et al., 2025). It was thought to be rare in malaria endemic regions because of increased mothers' malaria immunity with transplacental passage of maternal antibodies (IgG) to the fetus, placental structure acting as a barrier to transmission of parasite from the mother to the infant and the fetal hemoglobin (HbF) having some protective effect against malaria infection (Amaratunga, 2011; Patterson et al., 2026). Recent studies report far higher rates than expected.

A 2020 global analysis found congenital malaria in about 7% of newborns across malaria-endemic countries, with rates reaching 46% in some Nigerian studies (Bilial et al., 2020). National prevalence of 12.7 % has been reported in Nigeria (Odeniran et al., 2026), in Uganda the rate is 6.1% (Hangi, et al., 2019), and in the Democratic Republic of Congo 2.4% by DNA testing compared to less than 1% by traditional microscopy (Tshiongo et al., 2025), showing that some cases go undetected.

High prevalence of malaria in pregnancy and in the perinatal period, reduced effectiveness of anti-malaria prophylactic therapy, poor compliance to medications, drug resistance with high degree of treatment failure, increased awareness and improved diagnosis all contribute to the increasing prevalence CM. (Kokori et al., 2025; Omidiji et al., 2025; Tshiongo et al., 2025).

We describe three neonates with confirmed congenital malaria who were born to booked mothers who received standard antimalarial prophylaxis. All three cases were symptomatic and occurred within six months at a facility in Nigeria. What strikes us is the consistent pattern: every mother had documented malaria infection in labour or within 7 days postpartum, during which period the babies also became symptomatic. This temporal relationship suggests that maternal malaria status in the final weeks of pregnancy, intrapartum or in the immediate postpartum period deserves attention as a marker for neonatal risk. Early recognition of this risk could improve diagnosis of CM and reduce unnecessary investigation and treatment for bacterial infection in sick babies who have congenital malaria.

CASE SERIES: SETTING AND METHODS

We identified three cases of congenital malaria over a six-month period from September 2025 to January 2026 at a private healthcare facility providing maternity and newborn services in south-south Nigeria. The facility operates in a region where malaria transmission occurs year-round and *Plasmodium falciparum* is the dominant parasite species. We reviewed medical records for any newborn with confirmed malaria parasites in blood drawn within seven days of birth as well as those of their mothers. Maternal age, obstetric history, antenatal care attendance, antimalarial medications given with stated compliance, timing of any maternal fever or parasitemia, delivery details, and neonatal birth weight and vital signs were recorded. Neonatal data included date of birth, presentation of clinical symptoms, complete blood counts, blood culture results, and malaria testing results. Laboratory diagnosis of malaria used blood smear microscopy with Giemsa stain, the standard method available at the facility. Trained laboratory staff examined thick and thin blood films, identified parasite species and calculated the number of parasites per microliter when parasites were detected. Laboratory results are in Table 1.

CASE PRESENTATIONS

Case 1: Preterm Baby with Respiratory Distress Syndrome and Perinatal Maternal Malaria

A 34-year-old pregnant primigravida with a large uterine fibroid went into labor at 29 weeks and delivered by emergency caesarean section. She had attended regular antenatal visits and received three doses of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine. The male baby weighed 1.54 kg with Apgar scores of 6, 8, and 10 at one, five, and ten minutes. He received early rescue surfactant therapy for respiratory distress syndrome

and respiratory support with Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (CPAP) for 72 hours with good response. On day six of life, he developed a fever of 38.8 degrees Celsius, stopped feeding, and vomited twice. Blood cultures showed no bacteria, but the malaria test came back positive for Plasmodium falciparum with 58 parasites per microliter. He received artemether-lumefantrine twice daily for three days and recovered completely by day ten of life. Malaria retesting seven days after treatment was negative. The mother remained well after delivery until day four postpartum when she developed fever and headache. Post operative sepsis work-up were all negative and malaria testing was positive. She was treated with artemether-lumefantrine and recovered quickly.

Case 2: Term Baby with Intrapartum Maternal Malaria

A 24-year-old primigravida had an uncomplicated pregnancy and vaginal delivery at term. Her male baby was born in good condition with Apgar scores of 9 and 10, weighing 4.1 kg. He appeared healthy initially but later on day one of life, he developed a fever of 38.5 degrees that persisted. His blood culture yielded no growth, but malaria testing was positive with 95 parasites per microliter and he received oral artemether-lumefantrine for 3 days and was fever free from the last day of treatment. Malaria test done one week post treatment was negative. The mother had received 6 doses of standard antimalarial prophylaxis during pregnancy but developed fever during labor and tested positive for Plasmodium falciparum with 740 parasites per microliter. She also commenced on oral artemether-lumefantrine after delivery for 3 days with good recovery.

Case 3: Term Baby with Postpartum Maternal Malaria

A 35-year-old woman with four previous pregnancies and children delivered by caesarean section at 38 weeks for cephalopelvic disproportion. Her female baby had Apgar scores of 8 and 10, and birthweight of 4.9 kg. On day two of life, she developed fever of 38.9 degrees. Sepsis screen done was negative but malaria testing was positive for Plasmodium falciparum with 57 parasites per microliter. She received oral artemether-lumefantrine with improvement and fever subsided on the third day of treatment. The mother had received six doses of antimalarial prophylaxis during pregnancy. Two days after delivery she developed fever and tested positive for malaria. She was treated and recovered without complications.

Table 1. Laboratory Findings in Three Neonates with Congenital Malaria and Their Mothers

Case/Date	Hb (g/dL)	PCV (%)	WBC ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	Neut (%)	Lymph (%)	Mono (%)	Plt ($\times 10^3/\text{L}$)	MP	Parasites/ μL
Case 1 Neonate	12.9	37	14.5	31.5	60.0	7.7	202	Positive	58
Case 1 Mother	10.5	37	10.8	66	24.1	7.4	303	Positive	487
Case 2 Neonate	14.7	44	5.6	55.1	36.2	8.2	219	Positive	95
Case 2 Mother	10.3	33	7.2	58.4	28.7	11	147	Positive	740
Case 3 Neonate	15.2	44	15.2	64.1	28.6	6.9	174	Positive	57
Case 3 Mother	10	30	5.9	61.5	30.8	6.6	148	Positive	1,309

DISCUSSION

Three cases of CM within six months is significant in a region where cases are supposedly uncommon and support reports of its increasing prevalence (Danwang, et al., 2020; Gebremichael, 2025; Odeniran et al., 2025). Most cases of CM in endemic areas are asymptomatic, unlike in non-endemic regions, with spontaneous clearance of parasitemia within few days (Abolodjeet al., 2020; Oluwafemi et al., 2025). Some are however symptomatic often with non-specific clinical features such as fever, vomiting jaundice, poor feeding, irritability and hepatosplenomegaly similar to those of neonatal sepsis. The three cases presented all had fever, a feature common in many disorders. Fever in a newborn typically triggers full

sepsis workup with empirical antibiotics usually started even before neonatal sepsis is confirmed because of its potentially adverse consequences.

Many cases of CM have been reported from both within and outside Nigeria (Andarge et al., 2025; Gebremichael et al., 2025; Kajoba et al., 2021; Olupot-Olupot et al., 2018; Oluwafemi et al., 2025; Sher and Latif, 2021) with the mothers often well, or with negative or unknown state of malaria parasite. Remarkable in this case series is that all the babies and their mothers were symptomatic with malaria parasites in their blood during labor or within seven days of delivery. This temporal relationship noted calls for a high index of suspicion for CM in babies of such mothers especially in the absence of known risk factors for neonatal sepsis. Also worth mentioning was the easy and early access to diagnosis and treatment for both babies and their mothers in these cases, propelled by existing protocols for the management of fever in the facility which likely contributed to early diagnosis and favorable outcomes obtained.

The identified plasmodium species following testing in all cases was *Plasmodium falciparum* which was not surprising considering that it is the most common culprit in malaria endemic regions, though *P. vivax* and *P. malariae* are frequently implicated in non-endemic or meso-endemic settings. Also of note was the low parasite density in the babies which tends to support the proposal that HbF and maternal immune IgG may not completely prevent congenital malaria rather impairs cytoadherence of parasitized RBCs in the first few months of life causing reductions in parasite densities and attenuation of the virulence (Amaratunga et al., 2011).

The plasmodium species identified in each case was *Plasmodium falciparum* which was not surprising considering that it is the commonest specie that cause malaria in endemic regions with *P. vivax* and *P. malariae* are frequently implicated in non-endemic or meso-endemic areas. Of note also was the low parasitemia in the neonates even while they were symptomatic supporting the proposal that HbF and maternal immune IgG do not completely prevent congenital malaria rather, they impair cytoadherence of parasitized RBCs in the first few months of life causing reductions in parasite densities and attenuation of the virulence (Amaratunga et al., 2011).

All three mothers were booked, had regular ANC and received standard antimalarial prophylaxis but still developed malaria. This raises concern over the drug failure which could be from drug resistance, use of substandard drugs, incomplete dosage or sub optimal drug metabolism/absorption. *Plasmodium falciparum* has been documented to be resistant to Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine, the standard prevention drug for malaria in pregnancy threatening the effectiveness of intermittent preventive treatment during pregnancy (IPTp) in sub-Saharan Africa (Amimo et al., 2020; van Eijk et al., 2019). This underscores the need to adhere to the strategic framework for malaria prevention and control during pregnancy which includes three interventions: intermittent preventive treatment (IPT), use of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) and adequate case management of malaria illness and anaemia (Okova et al., 2024), rather than rely solely on chemoprophylaxis. Two of the three mothers were first time pregnant women (primigravida) while one has been pregnant more than once (multigravida). Our finding supports reports from most studies that the primigravida were more vulnerable to malaria than other pregnant women (Ali, 2022; Okiring et al., 2019). Simon-Oke (2019) however reported greater vulnerability to malaria among the multigravida.

All three babies recovered completely within days of starting antimalarial therapy with oral artemether/lumefantrine combination suggesting that this therapy is effective against *Plasmodium falciparum* parasites. None received antibiotics except for the preterm baby who was already on it before malaria diagnosis was made. Issues regarding congenital malaria thus seems to lie more with preventing malaria transmission to the baby and early recognition; we hope that observations made in this case series would be further explored to address the later.

CONCLUSIONS

These three cases teach us that congenital malaria is not a diagnostic curiosity but a real and preventable problem even in malaria endemic regions. While efforts to address failure of chemoprophylaxis should be intensified and mothers encouraged to adhere to the three key principles of malaria prevention in

pregnancy, we recommend that healthcare workers obtain maternal malaria history and status routinely when evaluating neonates with fever, especially in the 1st week of life. Positive maternal history or evidence of recent malaria should prompt immediate malaria testing for the baby especially in the absence of risk factors for neonatal sepsis.

REFERENCES

1. Abolodje E, Jiya NM, Onankpa B, Audu IL. Congenital malaria: Prevalence, clinical presentation, and clinical outcome. *Calabar J Health Sci.* doi: 10.25259/CJHS_55_2020
2. Ali, R. (2022). Malaria Prevalence among Pregnant Women in Relation to Parity, Gestation Period and Age in Gombe, North Eastern Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 26(6), 1063–1066. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jasem.v26i6.10>
3. Amaratunga, C., Lopera-Mesa, T. M., Brittain, N. J., Cholera, R., Arie, T., Fujioka, H., Keefer, J. R., & Fairhurst, R. M. (2011). A role for fetal hemoglobin and maternal immune IgG in infant resistance to *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria. *PloS one*, 6(4), e14798. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0014798>.
4. Amimo, F., Lambert, B., Magit, A., Sacarlal, J., Hashizume, M., & Shibuya, K. (2020). *Plasmodium falciparum* resistance to sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine in Africa: a systematic analysis of national trends. *BMJ global health*, 5(11), e003217. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-003217>
5. Andarge, B. D., & Almaw, K. (2025). Congenital malaria in a neonate born in a malaria-endemic area: a case report. *Journal of medical case reports*, 19(1), 434. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13256-025-05525-3>.
6. Bilal, J. A., Malik, E. E., Al-Nafeesah, A., & Adam, I. (2020). Global prevalence of congenital malaria: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *European journal of obstetrics, gynecology, and reproductive biology*, 252, 534–542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2020.06.025>.
7. Danwang, C., Bigna, J. J., Nzalie, R. N. T., & Robert, A. (2020). Epidemiology of clinical congenital and neonatal malaria in endemic settings: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Malaria journal*, 19(1), 312. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-020-03373-8>.
8. Gebremichael, Y. L., Hagos, H. H., Reta, B. K., Woldu, T. B., Berhe, K. R., Gebrearegay, F. G., & Tsegay, G. K. (2025). Neonatal and congenital malaria (NCM): a case series in the Tigray region, northern Ethiopia. *Malaria journal*, 24(1), 210. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-025-05466-8>.
9. Hangi, M., Achan, J., Saruti, A., Quinlan, J., & Idro, R. (2019). Congenital Malaria in Newborns Presented at Tororo General Hospital in Uganda: A Cross-Sectional Study. *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene*, 100(5), 1158–1163. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.17-0341>.
10. Kajoba, D., Ivan Egesa, W., Jean Petit, H., Omar Matan, M., Laker, G., Mugowa Waibi, W., & Asiimwe, D. (2021). Congenital Malaria in a 2-Day-Old Neonate: A Case Report and Literature Review. *Case reports in infectious diseases*, 2021, 9960006. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9960006>.
11. Kokori S, Konam JK, Nwankwo E, Okafor C. Prevalence and determinants of congenital malaria among neonates delivered at a tertiary health center in Southeast Nigeria. *Trop Med Health*. 2025;53(1):40.
12. Odeniran, P. O., Paul-Odeniran, K. F., & Ademola, I. O. (2026). Congenital malaria in Nigeria: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Parasitology international*, 110, 103147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parint.2025.103147>.
13. Okiring, J., Olwoch, P., Kakuru, A., Okou, J., Ochokoru, H., Ochieng, T. A., Kajubi, R., Kamya, M. R., Dorsey, G., & Tusting, L. S. (2019). Household and maternal risk factors for malaria in pregnancy in a highly endemic area of Uganda: a prospective cohort study. *Malaria journal*, 18(1), 144. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-019-2779-x>

14. Okova, D., Lukwa, A. T., Oyando, R., Bodzo, P., Chiwire, P., & Alaba, O. A. (2024). Malaria Prevention for Pregnant Women and Under-Five Children in 10 Sub-Saharan Africa Countries: Socioeconomic and Temporal Inequality Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21(12), 1656. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21121656>
15. Olupot-Olupot, P., Eregu, E. I. E., Naizuli, K., Ikiror, J., Acom, L., & Burgoine, K. (2018). Neonatal and congenital malaria: a case series in malaria endemic eastern Uganda. *Malaria journal*, 17(1), 171. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-018-2327-0>.
16. Oluwafemi, Rosena & Folarin, Bamidele & Bello, Emmanuel & Irinyenikan, Theresa. (2025). Asymptomatic congenital malaria among neonates of mothers attending antenatal clinic in University of Medical Sciences Teaching Hospital, Akure. *International Journal of Advances in Medicine*. 12. 350-355. 10.18203/2349-3933.ijam20251930.
17. Omidiji, M. O., Lesi, F. E. A., Esezobor, C. I., Fajolu, I. B., Oyibo, W. A., & Daramola, A. (2025). Prevalence of congenital malaria in an urban and a semirural area in Lagos: a two-centre cross-sectional study. *Scientific reports*, 15(1), 10709. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-94800-w>
18. Patterson, C. A., Nabarro, L. E., Kumar, S., Nolder, D., & Chiodini, P. L. (2026). Congenital Malaria in Non-Endemic Settings: A Literature Review and Update on Diagnosis and Management. *Journal of travel medicine*, 33(1), taaf099. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jtm/taaf099>
19. Sher, A. and Latif, S. (2021) Congenital Malaria: First Case Report in Kuwait. *Advances in Infectious Diseases*, 11, 290-297. doi: [10.4236/aid.2021.113026](https://doi.org/10.4236/aid.2021.113026).
20. Simon-Oke, Adepeju. (2019). Prevalence of Malaria Parasites among Pregnant Women and Children under Five years in Ekiti State, Southwest Nigeria.. *Journal of Biomedicine and Translational Research*. 5. 5. 10.14710/jbtr.v5i1.3711.
21. Tshiongo, J. K., Kuseke, L., Maketa Tevuzula, V., Luzolo, F., Kafala, Y., Ngelesi, E., ... Schallig, H. D. F. H. (2025). Congenital malaria in newborns of mothers living in highly endemic parts of Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo. *Paediatrics and International Child Health*, 45(1–2), 26–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20469047.2025.2459964>.
22. van Eijk, A. M., Larsen, D. A., Kayentao, K., Koshy, G., Slaughter, D. E. C., Roper, C., Okell, L. C., Desai, M., Gutman, J., Khairallah, C., Rogerson, S. J., Hopkins Sibley, C., Meshnick, S. R., Taylor, S. M., & Ter Kuile, F. O. (2019). Effect of Plasmodium falciparum sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine resistance on the effectiveness of intermittent preventive therapy for malaria in pregnancy in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet. Infectious diseases*, 19(5), 546–556. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(18\)30732-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(18)30732-1).
23. WHO (2025) Malaria. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/malaria>.